

THE ROLE OF WORDS AND MELODY IN SINGING**Akhmedov Mukhtarali Askarovich**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7783713>

Annotation: In this article, there is detailed information about the compatibility of words and melody, the uniqueness of the musical melody that arises in the sound complex, the character, rhythm, measure and other characteristics of the melody depending on the content of the poem. information is provided.

Keywords: song, tune, word, content, composer, idea, law, process, literature, poem.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada so'z va kuyning bir-biriga mos kelishi, tovush majmuasida vujudga keladigan musiqiy kuyning o'ziga xosligi, she'rni mazmuniga qarab kuyning xarakteri, ritm, o'lchovi va boshqa xususiyatlari namoyon bo'lishi haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: qo'shiq, kuy, so'z, mazmun, bastakor, g'oya, qonun, jarayon, adabiyot, she'r.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о сочетаемости слов и мелодии, своеобразии музыкальной мелодии, возникающей в звуковом комплексе, характере, ритме, размере и других характеристиках мелодии в зависимости от содержания стихотворения. информация предоставлена.

Ключевые слова: песня, мотив, слово, содержание, композитор, идея, закон, процесс, литература, стихотворение.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", of May 30, 2019 " On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay", "Shakhrisabz", "Termez" and "Kokand" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 "On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts" Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 "Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3].Ensuring the development and prospects of the Republic of Uzbekistan depends on the changes taking place in the economic, social, political and cultural spheres, and in order to actively participate in such changes, high-

level general and special knowledge, intellectual capacity, broad outlook and skillful use of information communications are required. Based on these requirements, the training of pedagogic personnel is one of the most important tasks of today.

In the art of singing, the harmony of words and melody is very important in performance. Naturally, each musical tune that appears in the complex of sounds has its own special meaning. In its place, the word connected to it also expresses an important idea. Actually, the poem is finished first. A composer or a singer writes a melody for a word, feeling the idea, meaning, and power of expression. The more powerful the poem, the more powerful the melody should be and fully reveal the meaning of the word. What weight (finger, aruz) the poem is created in must correspond to a number of laws of the melody.[4]

Depending on the content of the poem, the character, rhythm, measure and other features of the melody are revealed. As mentioned above, in this process, the idea of the word creates the basis for the creation of the melody. If the words and the tone do not complement each other, it will not be well received by the listeners.

The performer should fully reveal the content of words and melody while singing. For this, first of all, he should fully study the existing poem, live in it, understand its essence, and ensure that the tone fully reveals the content of this poem. In some cases, it is necessary to pay attention to improvisation, to pay attention to the lengthening of vowels and vowels.[5]

The singer's vocal abilities are very important in words and melody. First of all, what kind of vocal capabilities does the singer have, and in what tones can he sing the vocal work in the performance. The singer must hear and perceive his performance correctly. This process is considered one of the important factors in the performance of a singer, he should even hear the melodies that are being accompanied by musical instruments, and he should have developed and mastered the skill of singing in harmony with them. It is appropriate to consider the following factors as important for the singer to deeply feel the words and melody of the piece of music, to enter into the spirit and image of the piece, and to be able to show the performer's capabilities of this piece:

1. Deep understanding of the poem text of the work;
2. Being able to reveal the content of the poem's text using the melodic structures;
3. Know the melodiousness of the melody and its rhythmic character;
4. Realizing the importance of vowel sounds in words and tones;

5. Knowing the methods of breath control in performance;
6. The possibility of obtaining middle climax and climax veils in words and melody.[6]

Taking into account the qualities that are important in performance, each of them has its own importance. Because, in expressing the general idea of the work, the content of music and words, their interpretation through the medium of melody, the rhythms and dynamics of the development of the melody. The beginnings and endings of each melody and phrase, the interharmony of the metro-rhythmic aspects of the melody, are aspects that represent the level of the singer's knowledge and capabilities. All the features in this process are musical factors necessary to express the inner and outer world of the work in harmony.

In addition to this, the internal laws of the musical work ensure that the performance will be at a high level. These regularities are defined by the features explained by the sound series, style structure, stable sounds and structural forms of the melody. Usually, each piece of music works on a specific sound system. The extent to which the movements are expressed is reflected in the skill of the composer and performer of the work. It should also be noted that there are Uzbek and Caucasian versions of the epics in the series "Gorogly".[7]

The revival of the performance is based on the interconnection of sounds in the structure of the structure. However, in this connection, it is very important that each piece of melody and sentences are separate, and within the framework of the work, the sentences are composed as a whole, and that the main and secondary sounds of the sound line are proportionally composed. In this sense, folk and classical art genres have their own formal composition. In the performance of folk music, especially in the types of performance based on badikhagoy, free interpretation, the composition of the work undergoes a change, albeit partially. However, the steady sounds forming the main system of this component are embodied based on the steady sounds in motion, their development process and aspects of completion.

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